

An image matching method for digital images using morphological approach

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Abstract : Image matching methods play a key role in deciding correspondences between two image scenes. This paper presents a method for the matching of digital images using mathematical morphology. The proposed method has been applied to real life images. The matching process has shown successful and promising results.

Keywords : Digital image, gradients, image matching, mathematical morphology.

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